

ISSUES OF LAW STRUCTURE AND ITS IMPROVEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

Aymuratov Sultanmurat Berdimurat uli

Navoi state mining and technologies

Nukus Mining Institute under the University

Work with youth, spirituality and enlightenment department designer

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Abstract. This article presents scientific-legal information about the current state and relevance of legal science and the application of law in our country, and the need for legal norms in the construction of a democratic society is analyzed.

Key words: Law, legal personnel, legal norms, legal science, citizen, concept.

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is considered the main legal factor in the establishment of a democratic legal state in Uzbekistan, and the continuous study of the role and importance of legal sciences in society, their meaning and essence, have led to the need to teach legal sciences and put them into practice. emits The State Program, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5308 on January 22, 2018, also defines specific measures to improve the training of highly qualified legal personnel. Also, the President's Decree No. PF-4947 of February 2, 2017 "On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was announced. It clearly states that the further development and liberalization of the economy is one of the five main priorities for the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021.

On April 13, 2018, based on the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On organizational measures to further improve the activities of the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. PQ-3666, it was decided to create wide opportunities for legal education. In order to implement this Decision, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 573 of July 24, 2018 was adopted and based on this decision "On the admission of graduates of the law colleges of the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Tashkent State Law University for the bachelor's degree" We can cite as an example of the reforms implemented in the development of legal sciences the regulation and the establishment of law colleges in each province.

The issues of applying the law and legal norms to practice and introducing them as a field of science go back to ancient history. In Central Asia, the 9th-12th centuries are called the "Renaissance of Islam", that is, the "Renaissance of Islam" is a vivid example of this.

Our grandfather Ubaidullah ibn Mas'ud Bukhari pays special attention to the "theory of laws" in his works. He believes that before the creation of laws, his theory should be laid out, designed for many years, and the solution of existing legal problems should be shown through sources.

They consistently and productively used the scientific heritage of jurisprudence of Eastern scholars. For example, Sh. L. Montesque (1689-1755) emphasized that the strength of the legal system directly depends on the quality, effectiveness and execution of laws. According to his views, the style of the law should be simple and clear, free from pomp and silence. Concepts in the law must be clear and exclude the possibility of different interpretations.

☐ It is appropriate to methodically analyze a number of problems regarding the analysis of the problems of legal science and legal practice:

☐ Currently, the quality of scientific monographs, brochures, textbooks, training manuals issued in legal sciences should be seriously controlled. Because these textbooks and training manuals should be of high quality and useful for use in training the legal personnel we train. Some scientists are indifferent to their research work and translate scientific and educational literature published in foreign countries and publish it under their own name. It is important for the development of the legal science of our country that these authors are called to order and appropriate measures to be taken against them. But in this situation, if the authors study and translate these foreign literatures and sources and carry out comparative analysis and research, these monographs, pamphlets, textbooks, training manuals will be a very useful and necessary source for the growing legal personnel can serve .

☐ The issue of training qualified legal personnel based on practice requirements is one of the urgent issues today. At the present time, it is necessary to consider the perfect connection of practice with legal sciences as one of our main tasks. Because it is important to emphasize that, on the basis of the teaching of legal sciences, the practical improvement of theoretical rules, the deepening of judicial reforms, and the introduction of wide use in law-making and the educational process will have a good effect. That is why we can achieve high goals in the development of legal sciences and in the training of qualified legal personnel through practical application.

☐ In order to raise the level of legal sciences, in addition to these, we need to establish international scientific relations. Today, along with the teaching of legal

sciences and the training of legal personnel, legal scholars are required to conduct comparative legal analysis of the experience and theory of foreign countries and conduct research.

☒ Knowledge of foreign languages and computer technology of scientific researchers is of great importance for the development of modern jurisprudence.

☒ It is necessary to start working with talented students, to regularly involve them in scientific research. Only then, in the future, it would be possible to select candidates for doctoral studies and professional legal fields from among them.

☒ In addition, the development of legal science is directly related to the practice of law enforcement. Decisions made by the court, the study of the accumulated experience of law enforcement and control bodies, its analysis and the formation of new views on the development of law.

☒ Science, technology and practice should be connected. In particular, the perspective of legal science, on the one hand, is to produce legal views related to the legal provision of current reforms, to create theoretical foundations, and on the other hand, it is directly related to the transition to an innovative economy and economy.

According to the results of the analysis and methodical research on this issue, legal education and science play a role in the establishment of a legal democratic state and civil society in our country, in creating the legal basis for the implementation of socio-economic, political, judicial and legal reforms, in providing legislation in our country, it can be said that it makes a worthy contribution to the protection of the rights and freedoms of citizens, and to the improvement of their legal consciousness and culture.

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